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COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION REPORT

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Abbreviations used in this document

AMARC	Association Mondiale des Radiodiffuseurs Communautaires (World Association of Community Radio Broadcasters)
WP	Work Package
BIPG	Bere Island Project Group
GR	Grassroot Wavelengths
GW	Grassroot Wavelengths
M-ITI	Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute
TTS	Text-to-Speech
UCC	University College Cork

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1. INTRODUCTION

Deliverable D4.2 reports on the communication and dissemination strategies, activities implemented and the related results collected in the scope of the Grassroot Wavelengths (GW) project. These activities aim to achieve the highest impact by implementing a thorough dissemination plan that adhered to the following objectives:

- raise awareness amongst selected target groups with respect to GW activities, outputs and benefits arising from the project for manufacturing value chains;
- promote willingness to make use of project's outputs among researchers and targeted industries;
- support the design and implementation of the exploitation plan of the partners.

The implementation of the dissemination plan has paid particular attention to the identification and the involvement of the target audiences for the project, which encompass two main groups. The first group is the media in general, including audiovisual channels, web, and print media. It includes both EC-managed media, such as CORDIS website, and blogs and newspapers with a special focus on media pluralism. The second group is made up of EU citizens and community radio activists.

Chapter 2 illustrates the strategies behind the communication and dissemination activities of Grassroot Wavelengths as means to ensure public awareness informed by a pilot-driven approach. **Chapter 3** describes the aims of the communication work undertaken in the project along with the guidelines followed to build inclusive forms of communication. Moreover, chapter 3 provides a detailed description (with facts and figures) of the tools employed in the project. **Chapter 4** provides an illustration of project-related events where consortium partners presented and promoted the project. **Chapter 5** contains a description of the results collected in the project in terms of publications; this

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chapter also offers an overview of the project final event. Finally, **chapter 6** illustrates all the activities that the WP4 conducted to support project partners in 3 different phases of the community radio development: access and deployment, consolidation, and outreach.

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2. PUBLIC AWARENESS IN GRASSROOT WAVELENGTHS

The GW project has invested several resources in the communication and dissemination of the project's work and results in order to ensure public awareness as well as the sustainability of community radios. Not by chance, public awareness in GW is based on a **pilot-driven approach**, according to which the pilot actions (in Ireland and in Romania) are driving the design and implementation of community radio, triggering a public awareness process. The activities of communication and dissemination are to be read in the light of the **community-centered participatory methodology** to digital social innovation that nurtures the project.

2.1 Communication and dissemination as parts of co-design and sustainability strategy

Communication and dissemination activities have been identified as measures to maximize the project impact, with the specific goal of increasing its outreach through the wide dissemination of project objectives, activities and outcomes towards various target groups, with the broader aim of increasing public awareness. In this respect, **communication and dissemination actions** have been considered **crucial components of the co-design** of innovation services around the use of the radio technology as well as **important means to ensure the project sustainability**. As a matter of fact, the involvement of local communities, journalists, policy-makers and other stakeholders as part of the participatory methodology supporting the design of community stations has been strongly supported by the project communication outputs (e.g. brochures, stickers, factsheets) and channels (e.g. social media, website) that have been created since M1. The connection with WP2, Community Actions, is indeed a key

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component as the population involved in pilot actions is the first target public for the dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities carried on by the consortium. Along these lines, the engagement and participation of local citizens is the necessary condition to ensure that radio stations can be sustainable, leveraging on the community building work undertaken during the project's course. In the light of WP4 tasks (focus of this documents), and T4.2 in particular, the first half of the project has been mainly devoted to dissemination and communication while the exploitation activities increased during the second half of the project, in particular through the press and academic publications. All these activities rely on the potential audiences (local citizenship, public authorities, experts, international organizations) included in the implementation plan, and mainly rooted in the networks of the consortium partners (AMARC, Active Watch MedAlert, BIPG).

2.2 Strategies

The goal to foster public awareness required the creation of conditions that allow people to collect relevant information, collectively engage in sense-making and building relations. Strategically, that has been achieved – throughout GW WP4 – by considering offline and online interactions as part of relational practices across different media, as well as by situating the communication into local contexts. In both cases, communication and dissemination reflected both content produced *by* the project, like events, communication material or scientific articles, and content produced *on* the project by other actors, such as journalists and radio practitioners.

The **convergence** and **adaptation** between the different communication channels has been guided by the aim of providing the GW project with: 1) a strong connection with the field of inquiry and action, maximizing the possibilities for the implemented technologies

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to be useful for the people involved in the fieldwork activities and for volunteers; 2) the capacity to innovate the domain of collective awareness platforms by leveraging two existing widespread channels – FM Radio and telephony – to create a space in which community partners participate actively in the decision making around the use of the radio technology to support their social innovation activities.

These two parallel processes of convergence and adaptation point to the overarching goal of communication, dissemination, and exploitation practices in GW, that is building relations at different levels (e.g. with institutions as well as with local communities). The following sections articulate how this has been achieved in the context of the project activities.

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3. COMMUNICATION

Communication is a key component of the GW project. In fact, questions concerning communication and language have been central since the beginning of project activities, with particular regards to the recipients of communication outputs. For example, all consortium partners engaged in a discussion over the production of the project's brochure, reflecting on the role of language and the related need to include all the different stakeholders involved in the project. The outcome of such collective reflection has been the development of two brochures (instead of only one), one thought out and shaped to specifically address communities, and the other one crafted to address institutional stakeholders.

In light of this, the whole consortium, and the WP4 members in particular, engaged in a process of self-reflexivity with regards to the role of communication in the project, arguing that communication is not just about expression (that is the presentation and the description of the project to an audience). Rather, it is mainly a collection of frames (Goffman, 1974) – specific fields of meaning that organize and give sense to events around us – which help structure how meanings and messages are presented to an audience, with the purpose to influence the choices people make about how to process that information. As a consequence, communication in GW has been understood and developed according to three main trajectories:

- Informing
- Building relations
- Integrating local and project media

In what follows, we describe these three trajectories and aims.

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3.1 Aims

3.1.1 Informing

Understanding communication as informing highlights the transmission of information in order to make the recipient aware of something: informing people about the establishment of a new community radio, a meeting with EU stakeholders, an upcoming publication concerning the project, etc. Here are two examples of information delivered through communication in the project:

1. from GW Facebook page, October 27, 2020

*The latest newsletter of Grassroot Wavelengths is out! Check all the recent news at the link below and get updated about what is going on in the project!*¹

2. from GW website, October 2020

*The journalists of Radio France International (RFI) Romania have interviewed Radio Civic volunteers in Romania. Simona Fortan from Radio Civic Varvoru de Jos, Mira Balan from Radio Civic Sfantu Gheorghe, and Liana Ganea from the Grassroot Wavelengths project partner ActiveWatch have had the chance to speak about their experience and expectations in regards to community radio.*²

These two examples show what communication as informing is mainly about a transmission of information in order to make the recipient aware of something: informing people about the availability of a project publication or informing different audiences about the activities undertaken by consortium partners.

¹ <https://www.facebook.com/GrassrootRadio/posts/784086432157804>

² <https://grassrootsradio.eu/?p=1620>

3.1.2 Building relations

Besides the transmission of information, communication entails the primary meaning of constructing a relation by **making something in common, sharing** something, participating in something (as the etymology of the word itself conveys: from Latin *communicare* "to share, divide out; communicate, impart, inform; join, unite, participate in"³). In this case communicating means becoming involved in a relation that pays attention to the identity and roles of the subjects (e.g. who are the people who participate in this relation? Who is in? Who is left out?) and to the character of the relation itself, which both precedes and takes shape during communication. Words relating to this mode are: consensus, community, participation, reciprocity, trust, care, subjectivity, symbols, and culture. Therefore relation here has a twofold meaning: (1) "reference to" something and (2) "bond with something/somebody". Here are two examples of this more complex understanding of communication in the project:

1. from GW newsletter, May 2020

Grassroot Wavelengths is by all means joining these efforts by arranging significant activities in its pilots sites. Indeed, besides our regular activities, starting with the beginning of March we focused more intensely on communicating information and organizing activities relating to the COVID-19 pandemic. In Ireland, for example, the local school in Bere Island has used the local community radio to maintain the link between teachers and pupils; in Romania, the efforts of Radio Civic have been devoted to keep the two local communities of Sfântu Gheorghe and Vârvoru de Jos informed from reliable official sources, as well as to communicate positive information related to the virus.⁴

³ <https://www.etymonline.com/word/communication>

⁴ <https://mailchi.mp/5398f054aaf9/grassroots-radio-newsletter-4832076>

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2. from GW press release on International Women's Day 2020

As people, women, men, workers, researchers, and activists engaged in the Grassroot Wavelengths project, we join the International Women's Day 2020, which UN Women has dedicated to the theme of Gender Equality. The Generation Equality campaign is bringing together people of every gender, age, ethnicity, race, religion and country, to drive actions that will create the gender-equal world we all deserve. In joining this campaign as well as other forms of demonstration, the Grassroot Wavelengths project is committed to mobilizing to end gender-based violence; we are calling for economic justice and rights for all; bodily autonomy, sexual and reproductive health and rights; and feminist action for climate justice. We want technology and innovation for gender equality; and feminist leadership.⁵

These two examples convey the meaning of communication as building relations insofar as they pay attention to the subjectivities involved in the content shaped, and they value the instances of care deployed by the community radio in Ireland and Romania during the COVID-19 pandemic.

3.1.3 Integrating local and project media

As mentioned, communication work in the GW project has paid particular attention to the different recipients of communication outputs. This attention is explained with the fact that we are talking about a project implemented in remote and rural communities in Europe, thus dealing with local cultures, habits, and traditions that local populations take in high regard. Therefore, WP4's work, in collaboration with WP2 (community engagement), has put efforts in order to value local peculiarities. These efforts resulted in the decision to

⁵ <https://grassrootsradio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/March-8-2020-Press-release.pdf>

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multiply communication channels in order to reach local populations, by using both already existing platforms and creating new ones.

The most significant effort in this respect has been the decision of communities in Romania to run communication platforms (website and Facebook page) to facilitate the communication as well as to increase the impact of community engagement activities.

Figure 1. Radio Civic homepage (<http://radiocivic.ro/>)

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Figure 2. Radio Civic Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/Katarlez>)

As we will see more in detail in the following sections, this decision to split communication platforms to adjust to means and messages to local needs proved to be a successful action insofar as it was able to foster recognition and participation of local communities. The idea of multiplying communication channels without disregarding issues related to the organization of work is by all means one of the most important lessons that the GW project can offer. As we shall see in the next section, these efforts of fostering inclusion and participation resulted in the reconsideration of the project initial name too.

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3.2 GUIDELINES

3.2.1 Building and promoting an inclusive communication

The need to adopt an inclusive communication increased the consortium's sensibility towards any potential obstacle to this goal. Reflections concerning the use of language conducted during the early meetings of consortium partners uncovered, for example, the need to avoid a language full of technical terms and difficult to be appropriated by general (and non-English) audiences (Dunbar-Hester, 2014). This awareness involved the project's original and official name as well (Grassroot Wavelengths) insofar as the term "wavelengths" has been considered not so easy to pronounce and write for non-English speakers, and typical of tech-savvy people, thus quite distant from local communities. Therefore, the consortium decided to adopt the name "Grassroot Wavelengths" in all communication outputs aimed at the general public (e.g. website, brochures, newsletters), starting from the logo of the project itself:

Figure 3. Project logo

The choice to use 'Grassroot Radio' as project name, while leaving 'Grassroot Wavelengths' in all official reports and documents, proved to be an easier and more

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understandable phrase able to convey a clearer connection between the content of the project and its name, reflecting the practical general aim of the project: building radio stations with and for the people.

Additionally, in line with the guidelines illustrated in the Interim Communication and Dissemination Report delivered at M13, the consortium adopted some guidelines in order to develop a common language, sensitive towards the people encountered during research activities. In general, language (written, oral, visual) was meant to reduce stereotypes and discrimination in terms of gender, ethnicity, class, age, religion, ableness, education, technical literacy. It was remarked that the use and perception of language is cultural and context-based, so what might be a fair phrase (e.g. 'the elderly') for one context can be experienced differently in another context. What follows are some examples:

- **Use the plural form for both nouns and pronouns**

<i>Example with Bias</i>	<i>Example with Bias Removed</i>
“Each person should support Grassroot Wavelengths regardless of his level of technical knowledge”	“Each person should support Grassroot Wavelengths regardless of their level of technical knowledge”

- **Use neutral nouns**

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<i>Example with Bias</i>	<i>Example with Bias Removed</i>
“We would like to address the government’s spokesman to promote the project”	“We would like to address the government’s spokespersons to promote the project”

- **Use feminization in order to make female referent visible**

<i>Example with Bias</i>	<i>Example with bias removed</i>
“Each participant can share his ideas about show schedules to local broadcasters”	“Each participant can share his/her ideas about show schedules to local broadcasters”

- **Vary your choice of pronouns when you want to give examples that emphasize the action of an individual. Ideally, choose pronouns that work counter to prevailing stereotypes (Desprez-Bouanchaud, Doolaeye, Ruprecht, and Pavlic, 1999):**

- **to counter the stereotype that women are not tech-savvy whereas men are:**

Example 1

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<i>Example with bias</i>	<i>Challenging example with bias removed</i>
The research participant is not alone in understanding how to use the RootIO platform. Her difficulties in gaining a comprehensive understanding are shared by a large group of people.	The research participant is not alone in understanding how to use the RootIO platform. The difficulties in gaining a comprehensive understanding are shared by a large group of people.

Example 2

<i>Example with Bias</i>	<i>Challenging example with bias removed</i>
A hacker is not a person who breaks into or otherwise violates the system integrity of remote machines with malicious intent, but he constantly seeks further knowledge, freely shares what he has discovered, and never intentionally damage data.	A hacker is not a person who breaks into or otherwise violates the system integrity of remote machines with malicious intent, but she constantly seeks further knowledge, freely shares what she has discovered, and never intentionally damage data.

- **to avoid reinforcing gender-based division of labor**

Example 1

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<i>Example with Bias</i>	<i>Challenging example with bias removed</i>
Recent research points out that engineers often neglect their wives and children.	Recent research points out that engineers often neglect their families .

Example 2

<i>Example with Bias</i>	<i>Challenging example with bias removed</i>
Carl and Joan both have full time jobs; he helps her with the housework	Carl and Joan both have full time jobs; they share the housework

- **Practice use more neutral nouns. Some examples open to integration**

Traditional	Alternative
user	participants; people
man	individual; women and men, person
mankind	humanity, human kind, humans,
mother tongue	native tongue

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fatherland	nativeland
manpower	workforce

3.2.2 Beyond language: building an inclusive context

On a more general level, looking at contextual aspects beyond pattern of language, the communication team has been involved in larger reflections concerning the importance of fostering diverse and inclusive participation in research activities conducted in the project (Sciannamblo et al., 2019; Cibirin et al., 2020). For example, it has been noted that the environment of community radio tends to be typified by “geeky” identities and that the activists' inclusive ethos can be hampered by persistent issues of race, class, and gender (Dunbar-Hester, 2014). Therefore, in co-design activities a great amount of attention should be paid to differences in power relations among the actors involved in the development of technology. This is all the more true in projects, such as Grassroot Wavelengths, that involve different types of actors with different power to shape the construction of community radios: regulators, communities, researchers, funding agencies. Since its inception, the project has been committed to building an inclusive context through the adoption of a participatory mindset and the support of marginal actors in the co-creation of technology. At the same time, we found that there are specific institutional, cultural, social dynamics that need to be considered in every context. Therefore, it is clear that empowerment through co-creation of technology is not a taken-for-granted issue, but it is a situated activity of ongoing negotiations between the designers, the technology, and all the different stakeholders. The designers should

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definitely work to identify who are the marginal actors in specific situations, and to support them to find ways to express and reach their needs. However, this is not enough.

3.3 TOOLS

Grassroot Wavelengths can count on a diverse set of communication tools that serve multiple purposes. Tools available for external communication activities include: the project website (<https://grassrootsradio.eu/>), the Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/GrassrootRadio>), the Twitter page (<https://twitter.com/GrassrootsWaves>), newsletters, brochures, stickers, factsheets, press releases, deliverables, and publications.

The list of tools comprises both textual forms (such as press releases, factsheets) and media forms (such as the website and the Facebook page), a distinction that could be useful in order to understand the different forms of communication that these tools enable. For example, press releases, publications (e.g. papers, books), and deliverables mostly consist of closed narratives made up of written verbal text, with a finite number of authors, performing a top-down form of communication. The newsletter resembles press releases, publications, and deliverables in terms of being a written text, but it can become a multimedia text with the presence of links that connect to other textual forms such as video or audio tracks. Brochures, factsheets and stickers are syncretic texts in that they combine different languages and expressive forms such as images and words, which follow a coherent and strategic expressive line. The website and the social media pages are media forms comprising different kinds of text, languages and formats, organized through specific rules, conventions, channels (e.g. posts, comments, etc.), and technical configurations.

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In Grassroot Wavelengths, the website and the social media pages promote two different processes of communication in a strategic manner: the website provides information and updates about the project without enabling interaction, whereas the purpose of the social media is to spread information about the project and to deliver other content related to the project (e.g. critical analysis, news, etc.), which may add sense to the activities and goals of the project. Along with these media tools, we should not forget that physical presence, ordinary encounters, and the radio itself are also powerful means to cultivate public awareness. In this respect, the focus on the radio and the presence of the World Association of Community Radio Broadcasters (AMARC) as communication WP's leader have ensured a significant promotion of the project through community radio stations in Europe. The communication tools described in more detail in the next sections serve the main goals of communication and dissemination in Grassroot Wavelengths, that is informing about activities and events, disseminating results to multiple audiences contributing to shared meaning-making, and building relations able to foster public awareness.

3.3.1 Website

Being online is an essential requirement for achieving the maximum impact in terms of communication. Therefore, Grassroot Wavelengths has developed a basic version of the project website at M5, containing all the relevant information about the project and related topics (project objectives, information, news, event announcements, public reports, analysis, links to related initiatives). The website has been constantly updated with news elaborated by AMARC and other project partners.

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Figure 4. Website homepage (<https://grassrootsradio.eu/>)

As it is visible through the screenshot itself, the website offers a general introduction in Portuguese and Romanian, besides English, so as to ensure its community outreach. Moreover, the website features social media feeds with the Twitter and Facebook pages in order to give a broader overview of news and updates concerning the project.

At M12 a more intense news production activity started in parallel with the increase of events attended as well as the availability of early research findings. In this respect, AMARC – as leader of WP4 – proposed to elaborate a weekly news feed according to which each partner is supposed to contribute a news regarding its own activity. The proposal was well received, therefore the activity of storytelling around the project has been reinforced, resulting in the production of **53 total news**. Moreover, analytics provided by Google has been implemented into the website starting from M15, and they have been regularly analyzed to improve website efficiency. The following table summarize some key data concerning the website:

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News produced	53
Users⁶	2.026
Sessions⁷	2.855
Bounce rate⁸	64,34%
Pageviews⁹	6.066

Table 1. Website data

As shown in the table, the website attracted 2.026 users, for a total of 2.855 sessions. The pageviews have been 6.066 with a bounce rate of 69.9%. Considering all these data, we can say that the website performance is generally good, especially if we take into account the fact that, according to social media marketing experts, the benchmark bounce rate for non e-commerce website is 35-60%, and 65-90% for the category “dictionaries, blog, portals”¹⁰.

3.3.2 Social media

In parallel with the website, Facebook and Twitter accounts have been opened at M5 in order to increase the outreach of the project. Facebook and Twitter feeds have been implemented into the website so as to provide a convergent communication. The main goal of the Facebook and Twitter pages has been sharing content related to the project,

⁶ Users who have initiated at least one session during the date range.

⁷ A session is the period time a user is actively engaged with the website, app, etc. All usage data (Screen Views, Events, Ecommerce, etc.) is associated with a session.

⁸ The percentage of single-page sessions in which there was no interaction with the page.

⁹ Pageviews is the total number of pages viewed. Repeated views of a single page are counted.

¹⁰ <https://cxl.com/guides/bounce-rate/benchmarks/>

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produced both by the consortium (e.g. news on the website, upcoming events, new publications, research outputs) and by others (e.g. critical analysis, news, etc.) related to the goals of the project, so that to foster participation and engagement. Moreover, given the grassroots and local-based character of the project, a local website (<http://radiocivic.ro>), a Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/groups/275940083032046/>) and WhatsApp groups were born in Romania, with the support of the consortium, in relation to the two community radio stations of Radio Civic in Sfantu Gheorghe and Varvoru de Jos. As already mentioned, this convergence between project's official and local channels implemented to adapt means and messages to local needs proved successful in terms of outreach and engagement. The following tables show data on Facebook and Twitter performance elaborated as of December 21, 2020:

PAGE REACH TOTAL (28 days)	PAGE ENGAGEMENT TOTAL (28 days)	ENGAGEMENT RATE
409.181	36.741	8,9%

Table 2. Grassroots Radio Facebook Page

PAGE REACH TOTAL (28 days)	PAGE ENGAGEMENT TOTAL (28 days)	ENGAGEMENT RATE
16.089.736	14.789	0,09%

Table 3. Radio Civic Sfantu Gheorghe Delta Facebook Page

IMPRESSIONS	ENGAGEMENTS	ENGAGEMENT RATE
109.860	1929	1,76%

Table 4. Grassroots Radio Twitter Page

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As the data shown, the general performance of the project's social media channels (Facebook and Twitter) was rather positive. To date (December 21, 2020), the Grassroots Radio Facebook page registers **247 followers**, while the Grassroots Radio Twitter profile can count on **153 followers**. The Radio Civic Facebook page, created in July 2019, has been quite active and appealing, reaching **2081 followers**.

In terms of Facebook analytics, we considered data belonging to the page level as the unit of our analysis. We collected data signaling the level of Reach and Engagement. The former is defined by Facebook as "The number of people who had any content from your Page or about your Page enter their screen. This includes posts, check-ins, ads, social information from people who interact with your Page and more. (Unique Users)", while the latter indicates "The number of people who engaged with your Page. Engagement includes any click or story created. (Unique Users)".

At the page level, we have analysed the **reach** and **engagement** on the basis of 28 days, as it provides a more comprehensive view than the daily statistics¹¹. A total number of 409.181 users were reached by the official project page, while a total number of 16.089.736 has been reached by the Radio Civic Facebook page. A total number of 36.741 engaged with the project Facebook page, resulting in a very positive engagement rate of 8,9%¹². As for the engagement level of the Radio Civic Facebook page, a total number of 14.789 engaged with the contents of the page over 17 months, resulting in an engagement rate of 0,09%.

As far as Twitter insights are concerned, the project account has registered a total number of 109.860 impressions (according to Twitter: how many times my tweet showed up in

¹¹ It is important to clarify that the reach rates over long periods are estimated and sampled as Facebook does not provide specific tools to calculate the reach of unique users.

¹² Engagement rate = Engagement/Reach

people's feeds) and a total number of 1929 engagements (according to Twitter: total number of times users has interacted with a tweet, with click on hashtags, username, links, retweet, replies, follows, likes), resulting in a positive engagement rate of 1,76%¹³. Despite the number of general followers is not very high, the positive result registered by both project Facebook and Twitter pages has to do with the fact that they involve a small, but very engaged audience.

3.3.3 Newsletter

One of the project communication and dissemination tools is the newsletter, which has been created to disseminate the main updates and stories regarding the project. The newsletter circulated through MailChimp, one of the most popular professional emailing solutions used to ensure the best delivery rate. The quarterly newsletter is structured according to three main sections: an editorial focusing on the main update, a section “events” describing both upcoming and recent events that project partners has joined or organized, and a technical section called “Voxbox”, delivering information about the state of the art of the community radio stations under construction in the pilot sites. The first newsletter has been delivered at M15 to 108 recipients, while the last has been sent at M36 to **156 recipients**. In total, **7 newsletters have been delivered**¹⁴, and collected in a proper section of the project's website¹⁵. The following table summarizes some key data:

¹³ According to digital marketing metrics, in 2019 the average engagement rate per post on Twitter across the higher education sector is 0,079%, and 0,062% in the non profit sector: <https://www.digitalmarketingcommunity.com/indicators/twitter-average-engagement-rate-across-industries-2019/>

¹⁴ The last one will be delivered at the end of M36 (December 2020)

¹⁵ https://grassrootsradio.eu/?page_id=1171

Total subscribers	156
Average open rate	38%
Average click rate	3,35%

Table 5. Newsletter metrics

The data show positive results in terms of open rate (the percentage that indicates how many successfully delivered campaigns were opened by subscribers), corresponding to 38%. Indeed, according to Mailchimp benchmarks, the average open rate registered in two sectors in which Grassroots Radio can be included, that is “non-profit” and “Social Networks and Online Communities”, are 25.17% and 21.06% respectively. A similar analysis holds true as far as the click rate (the percentage that indicates how many successfully delivered campaigns registered at least one click is concerned): the benchmarks related to “non-profit” and “Social Networks and Online Communities” sectors are 2,79% and 3,32%¹⁶.

Moreover, the network of Community Media Forum Europe (CMFE) with its more than 100 members (media organizations, media scholars, media activists) regularly received information about the project activities and advancements through AMARC’s newsletter.

3.3.4 Factsheets

Since the beginning of the project, 6 factsheets have been designed in order to disseminate GW key principles and components, distributed on the web (website, social media, communities, partners’ networks), and collected in a proper section on the website¹⁷.

¹⁶ <https://mailchimp.com/resources/email-marketing-benchmarks/>

¹⁷ Similar to newsletters, the last project factsheet will be published at the end of M36 (December 2020).

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N° 780890.

Figure 5. Factsheet section on the website

To keep the project’s environmental footprint as low as possible, printed copies have been limited to the dissemination of information in external events where online promotion is neither possible nor sufficient. The first factsheet focuses on the general theme of “Community Radio in the 21st Century”, describing the background in which GW is situated, carrying a map highlighting community media activity across Europe. The second factsheet describes the functionalities of RootIO, the technical platform combining low-power community FM with contemporary internet and mobile telephony communication technologies on which GW radio stations are based. The third factsheet provides an overview of TTS, a technology that understands text and natural language to generate synthesized audio output complete with appropriate cadence and intonation, to be integrated into the RootIO architecture.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N° 780890.

Grassroots Radio
FACTSHEET #02

ROOTIO

Technological changes
high connectivity
and participation all fits in a bucket

WHAT IS ROOTIO?

ROOTIO is the freemium technology stack facilitated within the GW project. In a nutshell it combines low-power community FM with contemporary internet communication technologies for a very low cost.

- An Android Mobile App to synchronize with the cloud-based studio to download and upload content, program information, emergency broadcasts, etc.
- An innovative integration with Text To Speech technologies
- SIP telephony (internet telephony) for conference calling and live talk shows
- Radio hardware (i.e. transmission equipment: FM transmitters, antennae, antennae towers, cables)
- Facilities for streaming, podcasts, and other contemporary audio channels

1. WEB BASED STUDIO (<https://rootio.eu>)

Instead of the typical production studio, the Rootio web based studio, among other things allows for:

- Creation and management of stations and networks of stations
- Upload of pre-produced audio content for broadcast (News, Podcasts, serialized programs) which can be transferred to local stations by voice call or digital download
- Automatically placing calls to stations, hosts, or listeners
- Receiving calls from anyone
- Full IVR interactions
- Full SMS interactions
- Creation of ads or community announcements through an IVR system through a publicized number
- Creation of call-in programmes, and/or programs using uploaded and downloaded content
- Definition of program hosts and scheduling talk shows
- SMS votes, comments, and emergency push notifications
- Monitoring of the performance of the transmission site

2. SMARTPHONE/ ANDROID APP

The Android RootIO phone app, which sits next to the FM transmitter, works together with the web-based

3. FM SETUP

The RootIO transmission sites consist of a low power FM transmitter (~50 Watt), an Android smartphone, solar power equipment, a 15-25 meter tower, and an FM antenna. The phone is connected to the FM transmitter using an RCA cable - this way whatever audio the phone is playing through its headphone connector is piped into the FM transmitter and broadcast to the surrounding community. The FM transmitter itself is connected to the antenna using 50 ohm RF cable and the antenna is hoisted atop a light (10Kg) telescopic fiberglass pole not exceeding 25 meters above the ground. The mobile phone and FM transmitter are hosted in a plastic case for protection against the environment and interference or theft. This ensemble is capable of broadcasting 24 hours

CONTEXT

RootIO facilitates the operation of low power FM radio stations in communities that depend on FM radio the most. Rather than have one station span a large area, RootIO advocates for the proliferation of more but smaller stations, each serving a local neighborhood or town, a segment of the would-be listenership of a large radio station. To this effect, RootIO stations are low power and cover a fraction of the area of a typical station, with lower cost implications for capital and operations. This also means that local issues can be easily discussed and deliberated, and local music and culture can be heard. That said, stations can also join together for regional or national programming.

Production site

In more detail... The Rootio architecture relies on 3 main components

1. WEB BASED STUDIO (<https://rootio.eu>)

studio to replace much of the functionality of a typical FM radio station. The phone hosts pre-recorded audio content like music or development programmes, which can also be updated through a mobile network. The RootIO app is capable of:

- Playing recorded audio content according to schedule and playlists that can be modified via the web-based studio
- Automatically answering/rejecting regular GSM calls from the cloud, allowing voice-quality live programming
- Reporting information about the station, including current location and system health, to the web
- Synchronizing and transferring digital information, from podcasts to emergency information

2. SMARTPHONE/ ANDROID APP

Depiction of interaction of various components in a RootIO station setup

The Grassroots Radio project is funded through the European Commission Horizon 2020 framework under the forward-looking Collective Accession Program (CAP).

Figure 6. Example of factsheet

The fourth and fifth factsheets are dedicated to the description of the methodology and results of the community engagement activities. The sixth and last factsheet will collect the numbers achieved by the project in all its parts.

3.3.5 Press releases

Press releases are communication formats usually prepared in conjunction with important achievements concerning the project or to highlight relevant events. Like newsletters and factsheets, press releases are also included in a proper section in the website.

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A first preliminary press release (in Portuguese) was delivered by Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute (M-ITI) in September 2017, before the starting date of the project, in order to spread the news about the funding received for the project. A second press release was disseminated at M6 in order to inform about two community radio station licenses (Radio Civic Vârvoru de Jos and Radio Civic Sfântu Gheorghe) issued in Romania. A third press release was released at M8, informing about the preparation work carried out in order to launch the community radio station in Bere Island. As shown in the table of publications in the next sections, the press releases have been well received by the local press, whose outputs have also been published into the website.

Two other press releases were disseminated in relation to two relevant events for both the project and the consortium. The first one was published in occasione of the World Radio Day 2020 and titled “World Radio Day 2020 — We are DIVERSITY. We are (Grassroots) RADIO!”; the second one was delivered to join the celebration of the International Women’s Day 2020, with the title “International Women’s Day 2020: We are Generation Equality”. These two documents were supported and disseminated through the international network of AMARC Europe.

3.3.6 Brochures, stickers, and posters

Grassroot Wavelengths' public engagement activities could also count on the availability of brochures, illustrated documents that describe the project. A first promotional brochure has been delivered at M6 (in coincidence with the Digital Social Innovation Fair attended in Rome, in June 2018) to disseminate general information about the project: goals, pilot sites, and technical information. A second brochure has been delivered at M12 with a specific focus on the rural areas (in Ireland, Portugal, and Romania) in which the project articulates its actions.

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Figure 7. Template of the brochure

In this case, as already mentioned, two types of brochures have been developed: one designed with a language addressing institutional settings, and a second one with a language addressing communities. The choice to develop two versions of the same brochure was based on the request of pilot partners, who realized that a document with a more accessible language was necessary in order to approach research participants and potential users of the radio in the different pilot sites. Moreover, the second brochure has been translated into Romanian language due to a specific request of colleagues from Romania, who asked to translate the original brochure in local language in order to meet local needs. Brochures are available on the website as other communication and dissemination outputs¹⁸.

¹⁸ At the following link: https://grassrootsradio.eu/?page_id=1169

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The promotion of the project was also made through stickers and posters, designed according to the project's visual identity developed by AMARC and printed by pilot partners, in coordination with AMARC, on the basis of local needs. Stickers have been produced for each radio station built as requested by local partners.

Figure 8. Bere island sticker

Figure 9. Oileáin sticker

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Figure 10. Radio Civic sticker

Together with brochures and stickers, posters, leaflets and banners have been printed to advertise the project, maintaining the general visual identity and adapting the content to the local needs:

Figure 11. Radio set with the project sticker

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Figure 12. Project banner in Sfantu Gheorghe

The following tables collect the numbers of printed dissemination outputs realized in Ireland and Romania:

Type of output	Number
Sticker	150
Brochure	70

Table 6. Dissemination outputs distributed in Ireland

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Type of output	Number
Sticker	1100
Brochure	150
Flyer	1100
Banner	10

Table 7. Dissemination outputs distributed in Romania

3.3.7 Radio interviews

The communication and dissemination of Grassroot Wavelengths’ results and updates could also leverage the AMARC’s network in Europe, which include around 270 community radio representing an estimated 8 to 10 million listeners and several thousands European and international listeners through partners’ social network pages. AMARC has engaged partner’s radio stations in interviews, radio shows and round table discussions on a variety of topics: innovation for dialogue, media literacy and participation, technological advancements, new legal frameworks (i.e. Romania). 7 interviews have been conducted throughout 2020 to disseminate the results achieved in the project and promote its innovative technologies (RootIO and text-to-speech) as well as community engagement activities. All the interviews’ audio files are available in a proper section of the website¹⁹.

¹⁹ At the following link: https://grassrootsradio.eu/?page_id=1556

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3.3.8 Tutorials

In order to encourage community radio stations to live broadcast all of the assemblies that the communities consider worth making public, the WP2 team in collaboration with WP4 team designed a set of tutorials in order to support communities, social groups and anyone interested in creating a community around a common interest or concern with live broadcasting using RootIO and a standard smartphone.

These tutorials were conceived with the aim to support citizens and/or community members in having access to public decision-making, and to communicate concerns, by clarifying important requirements (e.g. system of roles, tasks and rules that guides the stations) related to the **governance** of the radio stations.

[Click on the titles below to access the tutorials](#)

SETTING ROOTIO TO BROADCAST AN ASSEMBLY LIVE

This tutorial helps to create: a host on RootIO, a program, and a schedule.

USING THE PHONE FOR THE LIVE BROADCAST

This tutorial shows how to use the phone to broadcast the face-to-face dialogues, as well as the calls accepted/initiated by the host.

LIVE ASSEMBLY ON-AIR

RootIO offers the possibility to broadcast an assembly live. For this, we have already seen how to set the web interface and how to use the mobile phone during the live. Now, with this tutorial, we will describe the main scenarios of use.

RECORDING THE ASSEMBLY AND USING THE AUDIO FILES

There is also the possibility to record the assembly in order to broadcast it later and to work with the audio files. Let's see how with this tutorial.

Figure 13. List of tutorials available on the website

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Each tutorial helps the participant in undertaking all the steps necessary to achieve the live broadcast, from setting up RootIO to recording the assemblies. All the tutorials are collected and described in a proper section on the website²⁰.

²⁰ At the following link: https://grassrootsradio.eu/?page_id=1267

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4. EVENTS

Since the beginning of project activities, project partners have been devoting a significant part of their work to the dissemination and exploitation of the results collected in the different pilot sites by attending and organizing meetings and events. Events differ in aims and types, ranging from academic conferences to meetings with policy-makers to encounters with local communities.

The organization of and participation in project-related events during the last year of activities (2020) have been disrupted by the outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic. Nevertheless, consortium partners managed to participate in online events to promote the project as well as AMARC arranged to organize the project's final event. The following sections provide descriptions and data related to the events involving the project.

4.1 TYPES AND AIMS

The organization of and participation in events were central activities characterizing the communication and dissemination work. In particular, in the context of a participatory design approach, events enabled the formation of relations that favour the emergence of public awareness. To achieve this overarching goal, members of the consortium have participated in events organized by others, like conferences or dissemination activities, and they have engaged in organizing events of their own. The main target audiences involved in these events were local communities, public authorities, and academic networks. The following table provide a list of the events in which the project has been promoted as well as an overview of the audiences involved:

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NUMBER	NAME OF THE EVENT	LOCATION AND DATES	PARTNER	AUDIENCE
1	CAPSSI Connected Technologies for Social Good Workshop	14-15 Feb. 2018 Brussels, Belgium	M-ITI	Scientific community
2	WP3 development meeting (CereProc, M-ITI RootIO)	3-4 May 2018 Edinburgh, UK	CereProc	Scientific community
3	Digital Social Innovation Fair	5-9 June 2018 Rome, Italy	M-ITI, AMARC	Scientific community, general public, policy makers
4	MAZI summit	16-18 October 2018 Edinburgh, UK	M-ITI	Scientific community
5	Web Summit 2018	5-8 Nov 2018 Lisbon, Portugal	RTO, M-ITI	Industry
6	CRAOL Feile 2018	12-14 October 2018, Athlone, Ireland	UCC	Media
7	The road ahead for digital social innovation: How can the EU support tech as a force for empowerment and social impact?	April 26, 2019 Brussels, Belgium	AMARC	Scientific community, policy makers, civil society
8	Communities and Technologies Conference	June 6, 2019 Wien, Austria	M-ITI, UCC	Scientific community
9	Sensorium	June 8-9, 2019 Bratislava, Slovakia	M-ITI, UCC	Scientific community

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10	Oral History in the Digital Age Conference	28-29 June, 2019, Limerick, Ireland	Bere Island Projects Group, Bere Island Heritage Centre & UCC	Oral History Network of Ireland, community practitioners and academics
11	Development Studies Association of Ireland Summer School	5-6 June 2019, Cork, Ireland	UCC	Civil society
12	1st Conversational User Interfaces Conference	22-2 August 2019, Dublin, Ireland	M-ITI, CereProc	Scientific community
13	6th Conference of the Radio Research Section of the European Communication Research and Education Association (ECREA)	19-21 September, Siena, Italy	M-ITI, UCC, AMARC	Scientific community
14	Ethnographies of Collaborative Economi(es) Conference	25 October 2019, Edinburgh, UK	AMARC, M-ITI	Scientific community
15	Internet Festival	10-13 October 2019, Pisa Italy	UCC	Journalists, scientific community, civil society
16	CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems	April 2020, online	M-ITI	Scientific community
	CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems	April 2020, online	M-ITI, UCC	Scientific community
17	Participatory Design	June 2020, online	UCC	Scientific community

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	Conference			
18	European Association for the Study of Science and Technology+Society for the Social Studies of Science Conference 2020	August 2020, online	M-ITI, UCC, AMARC	Scientific community
19	Irish Island Innovation Summit	September 2020, online	BIPG, UCC	Civil society
20	NORDICHI – Nordic Conference on Human-Computer Interaction	October 2020, online	M-ITI, UCC	Scientific community
21	CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems	2021 forthcoming, online	M-ITI, UCC	Scientific community
22	The 24th ACM Conference on Computer-Supported Cooperative Work and Social Computing	2021 forthcoming, online	M-ITI, UCC	Scientific community

Table 8. List of project-related events

In total, the project has been involved in **22 events**, reaching an audience of nearly **1500 people**.

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5. EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS

Following the guidelines included in the grant agreement, each partner has focused on the effective dissemination of results deriving from the project's fieldwork and events. This dissemination activity has resulted in several different publishing venues in which the project has been presented and discussed. As the following section illustrates, these venues are academic journals, magazines, and newspapers.

5.1 ACADEMIC PUBLICATIONS

Since the beginning of the project, consortium members made efforts to disseminate findings from their research on the multiple aspects characterizing the project: community engagement work, the co-design of technologies (RootIO and text-to-speech), and the role of regulatory frameworks.

In terms of publications in academic peer-reviewed journals, the research and elaboration of such a diverse set of issues have been conducted by researchers engaged in different work packages in collaboration with pilot partners each time the project has had key findings to disseminate. Such a synergical work resulted in a significant and diverse number of academic publications (high impact conference proceedings, journal articles, and oral presentations), listed in the following table:

NUMBER	TITLE	DATE	DISSEMINATION VENUE	PARTNER
1	Institutioning and Community Radio. A comparative perspective	2019	Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Communities & Technologies - Transforming Communities	M-ITI, UCC
2	Co-designing collaborative care	2019	Ethnographies of Collaborative Economies Conference	AMARC, M-ITI

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	work through ethnography		Proceedings	
3	Who owns your voice? Ethically sourced voices for non-commercial TTS applications	2019	CUI '19: Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Conversational User Interfaces	M-ITI, CereProc
4	All Together Now: The Living Audio Dataset	2019	Interspeech 2019	M-ITI, CereProc
5	Co-designing convivial tools to support participation in community radio	2020	Radio Journal: International Studies in Broadcast & Audio Media	AMARC, M-ITI, UCC
6	Considerations for Implementing Technology to Support Community Radio in Rural Communities	2020	CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems 2020	UCC, ActiveWatch
7	"Human, All Too Human": NOAA Weather Radio and the Emotional Impact of Synthetic Voices	2020	CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems 2020	M-ITI
8	Research Journeys: Making the Invisible, Visual	2020	Proceedings of the 2020 ACM Designing Interactive Systems Conference	UCC
9	Implementing Text-to-Speech tools for Community Radio in Remote Regions of Romania	2020	Adjunct Proceedings of the 2020 ACM International Joint Conference on Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing and Proceedings of the 2020 ACM	M-ITI

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			International Symposium on Wearable Computers	
10	Participating through substituting and refusing	2020	Participatory Design Conference 2020	UCC
11	Low Powering: Challenges In The Co-Creation Of Local Community Radio Stations	2020	European Association for the Study of Science and Technology+Society for the Social Studies of Science Conference 2020 – oral presentation	M-ITI, AMARC, UCC
12	Shaping Social Innovation in Local communities: The Contribution of Intermediaries	2020	NordiCHI '20: Proceedings of the 11th Nordic Conference on Human-Computer Interaction: Shaping Experiences, Shaping Society	UCC, M-ITI
13	Being Regulated: Licence to imagine new technology for community radio	2021	The 24th ACM Conference on Computer-Supported Cooperative Work and Social Computing. CSCW (CSCW), in press 2021	UCC, M-ITI
14	Islandness and HCI	2021	ToCHI Special Issue on Rural Computing and HCI, in press 2021	UCC

Table 9. List of academic publications

5.2 MAGAZINES AND BLOGS

Leveraging the reinforcement of media pluralism as one of its central goals, Grassroot Wavelengths achieved significant results even in terms of press coverage. Press outputs on the project have indeed appeared on both local and international magazines and newspapers. The project also earned two mentions in the Horizon Magazine, the science and innovation magazine

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from the European Union. The following table contains a detailed list of press outputs developed around the project:

NUMBER	DATE	TITLE	NEWS SITE
1	September 2017	Madeira-ITI e Arditi já têm sete projectos aprovados no âmbito do Horizonte 2020 (Portuguese)	Dnoticias.pt
2	April/May 2018	Rural Radio, Open source toolkit RootIO is helping communities create their own micro radio stations	Make
3	June 2018	Ședința CNA de joi, 7 iunie 2018 (Romanian)	Media Expres
4	June 2018	RADIO-CONCURS / Frecvențele radio alocate la 7 iunie — lista cu voturile membrilor CNA (Romanian)	Media Expres
5	June 2018	Concurs radio CNA 2018. CNA decide câștigătorii celor 22 de frecvențe radio (Romanian)	Paginademedia.ro
6	June 2018	Madeira ITI envolvido em projecto europeu que cria rádios comunitárias (Portuguese)	Funchal Noticias.net
7	August 2018	Plans afoot for radio on a Cork island	Irishexaminer.com
8	November 2018	Carlos Moedas: The EU will fund more social innovation because it's the future of innovation	Horizon Magazine
9	December 2018	Grassroot Lenses: Primele frecvențe FM pentru radiouri comunitare românești (Romanian)	Alternativ.ro
10	January 2019	Hyperlocal radio and do-it-yourself	Horizon Magazine

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		networks bring information closer to home	
11	January 2019	Hyperlocal radio and do-it-yourself networks bring information closer to home	phys.org
12	January 2019	Hyperlocal radio and do-it-yourself networks carry data nearer to dwelling	Todaychan.com
13	January 2019	Islanders' radio ambitions on the right wavelength	southernstar.ie
14	April 2019	Bere Island's new radio station gets community on the right wavelength	southernstar.ie
15	May 2019	"Civic Radio has begun to release programs made by local communities for the first time" ("Radio Civic a început să emită în premieră programe realizate de comunități locale")	Mediafax.ro
16	May 2019	"Radio Civic began to broadcast programs made by local communities for the first time" ("Radio Civic a început să emită în premieră programe realizate de comunități locale")	orange.ro
17	June 2019	"Radio Civic began to broadcast programs made by local communities for the first time" ("Radio Civic a început să emită în premieră programe realizate de comunități locale")	Anchetatorul.ro
18	July 2019	EU initiative leads to world's 1st commercially available synthesised Irish voice	irishtechnews.ie

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19	July 2019	Virtuelles Archiv macht sich sichtbar (German)	thurgaukultur.ch
20	July 2019	Eu Tech Project Gives First Irish Synthesised Voice for Bere Island Radio Project	irishtechnews.ie
21	July 2019	Bere Island to pilot 'Siri' as Gaeilge	corkindependent.com
22	August 2019	Island radio gives digital voice to the people as Gaeilge	irishexaminer.com
23	December 2019	Hyperlocal radio puts down roots in Romania	European Journalism Observatory – en.ejo.ch
24	March 2020	Island says 'stay safe – but away'	Southernstar.ie
25	March 2020	Bere Island self-isolates as residents ask for no visitors	Irishexaminer.com
26	March 2020	Cork island with many vulnerable residents asks people not to visit	EchoLive.ie
27	April 2020	Comunități mici, fapte mari: #Episodul 1 – Mira, omul de bine de la kilometrul 0 al Deltei (Romanian)	Auzimdebine.ro
28	April 2020	"Poveștile de viață ale ucrainenilor la Radio Civic Sfântu Gheorghe"(Romanian)	Uur.ro
29	May 2020	În inima Deltei, pandemia de coronavirus e doar o știre la televizor (Romanian)	Observatornews.ro
30	May 2020	Bere radio station's Covid updates in seven languages for fishermen	Southernstar.ie
31	May 2020	Dunărea decimată: Eforturile de revitalizare a sturionilor ignoră cauzele braconajului (Romanian)	Balkaninsight.com
32	May 2020	Decimated Danube: Sturgeon	Balkaninsight.com

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		Revival Efforts Neglect Roots of Poaching	
33	June 2020	#Jurnal din redacție 23 (Romanian)	Cji.ro
34	June 2020	Poveștile de viață ale ucrainenilor la Radio Civic Sfântu Gheorghe(Romanian)	Uur.ro
35	July 2020	New irish digital outposts! Cape Clear and Sherkin Island launch community radio station	Irishtechnews.ie
36	September 2020	Using innovation and technology to connect, the irish virtual island summit podcast	Irishtechnews.ie
37	October 2020	Tanar in Europa Radio Civic, un post de radio realizat de voluntari (Romanian)	Rfi.ro

Table 10. List of publications on newspapers, magazines and blogs

5.3 FINAL EVENT

The second part of 2020 has seen significant efforts devoted to the organization of the Grassroot Wavelengths final event, which was coordinated by AMARC. Given the restrictions to the mobility imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic, the consortium agreed on organizing the final event online, taking advantage of this format to involve a diverse set of speakers.

Thanks to the AMARC's network, the event was hosted on the German Federation of community radios' (BFR) open source platform on December 17-18, 2020. The event took shape in three parts focused on the main aspects characterizing the project: technology and local communities, regulatory frameworks, engagement and inclusion. Consortium

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partners participated in all the sessions and in the round table, along with relevant guests such as audiovisual regulators and academic scholars.

Figure 14. Picture of the final event, round table on regulatory frameworks

The round table dedicated to the role of regulatory frameworks for the establishment and sustainability of community radio in Europe was a rather relevant session, with the participation of Oana Anghel (Adviser in the Legal and European Affairs Department National Council of Audiovisual of Romania), Roger Woods (Licensing Implementation and Spectrum Co-ordination Broadcasting Authority of Ireland), and Michael Nicolai, President of AMARC Europe.

The event was open and public, advertised on the project's website and social media channels²¹.

²¹ <https://grassrootsradio.eu/?p=1646>

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6. KNOWLEDGE SHARING

The intervention of AMARC in the project went beyond the direct assignments established by the Partner Agreement. Having in mind its statutory nature, AMARC Europe accompanied project partners in 3 different phases of the community radio development: access and deployment, consolidation, outreach.

6.1 ACCESS AND DEPLOYMENT

AMARC has a long term experience in audiovisual regulatory frameworks, at the regional and national level in Europe and, as a network, in many other countries around the world. Few years ago, the organization was part to the working group organized by EPRA, the European Platform of Regulatory Authorities in regards to community media, and had a pro active relationship with the EU promoting 2 public hearings on communication rights in the digital sphere and the key role of minority languages and community radios to promote cultural diversity and social cohesion.

- **Access:** In this context, access is meant to be the preparatory background information related to community broadcasters at the European level as well as the best practices of regulatory frameworks in Europe. While Irish colleagues could benefit from an existing equitable legislation for the access to airwaves for community radios, the Romanian case was the first attempt to obtain a community-based broadcasting licence. Duly documentation was shared with partners in order to follow the procedure according to the recommendations designed by the European Parliament and the Council of Europe.

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- **Deployment:** by deployment we intend to spotlight the technical recommendations for the set up and purchase of broadcasting devices (transmitters and antenna systems) for radios in Romania and Ireland. Thanks to its experience in setting up community radios, AMARC could orient partners to the best selection among different offers in line with the technical specifications, licencing and coverage needs.

6.2 CONSOLIDATION

The consolidation phase corresponds to all the support provided after the technical set up of radio stations, through detailed information sharing on:

1. **programme schedule:** AMARC supported the BIPG for the set up of a more coherent program schedule based on the capacities and objectives of the small scale radio;
2. **networking:** the favorable environment of the community media sector in Ireland provided AMARC with the possibility to establish regular relationships with key community radios in the country (ex, Near FM Dublin, Connemara Community Radio) since 2008. In 2010, AMARC Europe organized its Regional Conference and General Assembly in Dublin, in partnership with CRAOL, the Community radio national forum in Ireland. This relationship facilitated the approach to CRAOL from the Bere Islands Project Group and the newborn community antenna. In terms of impact, CRAOL facilitated an in-situ training from one of its volunteers and the radio could also access to the program exchange mechanism set up on a national level.

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6.3 OUTREACH

The outreach and impact at the local level has been enhanced by the recommendations of AMARC based on previous experiences. The communication effort towards local citizens, alongside traditional tools like stickers, posters and brochures in local languages, has been completed by the free distribution of small radio receivers to the local population. Roughly **1000 radio sets have been distributed** in the two locations in Romania with a significant effect not just in terms of listeners, but also in a symbolic perspective. A similar initiative is taking place in Bere Islands and Cape and Sherkin Islands in Ireland. After the initial proposal, AMARC accompanied partners in the selection of radio sets and their customization with the graphical identity of the project, with the duly EU official acknowledgement.

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